

Estimation of Stature Using Humerus Length among the Adult PopulationVivekanand¹, Kumari Rashmi², Birendra Kumar Sinha³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Surgery, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India³Professor & HOD, Department of Anatomy, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 15-04-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Stature estimation plays a vital role in forensic science, anthropology, and clinical practice, especially when dealing with incomplete skeletal remains. Among various skeletal elements, the humerus is a reliable bone for estimating stature due to its strong correlation with overall body height. However, the accuracy of stature estimation models varies significantly across different populations, necessitating the development of population-specific equations.

Aim: This study aimed to estimate stature using humerus length in an adult population and to develop a regression model specific to this population for forensic and anthropometric applications.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 140 adult participants. Humerus length and stature were measured using standardized techniques. Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to assess the relationship between humerus length and stature. A linear regression analysis was performed to develop a predictive model. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The study found a strong positive correlation between humerus length and stature ($r = 0.82$, $p < 0.001$). The developed regression equation was $\text{Stature (cm)} = 45.1 + 4.05 \times \text{Humerus Length (cm)}$, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) and explained 67% of the variation in stature. Gender-based analysis indicated slight differences in the regression equations for males and females, enhancing the model's accuracy.

Conclusion: Humerus length is a robust predictor of stature in the studied population. The regression model developed in this study provides a reliable tool for stature estimation, which can be particularly useful in forensic and anthropological contexts. Given the population-specific nature of these equations, similar studies are recommended in other regions to enhance the accuracy of stature estimation globally.

Recommendations: Future studies should focus on validating this model in different populations and exploring the inclusion of additional demographic variables to further refine the accuracy of stature estimation methods.

Keywords: Stature Estimation, Humerus Length, Forensic Anthropology, Regression Model, Population-Specific Equation.

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Introduction

Stature estimation is a critical component in the fields of forensic science, anthropology, and clinical practice, where it serves as a fundamental parameter for identifying individuals in both living and skeletal remains. Estimating stature from skeletal measurements is particularly valuable in situations where the complete body is unavailable, such as in mass disasters, criminal investigations, and archaeological excavations. Among the various skeletal elements, the long bones of the upper and lower limbs are frequently used due to their strong correlation with overall body height [1].

The humerus, one of the major long bones in the upper limb, has been extensively studied for its role in stature estimation. Several studies have demonstrated that the length of the humerus is strongly correlated with an individual's stature, making it a reliable predictor [2]. The accuracy of

such estimations is influenced by factors including population specificity, age, sex, and the methods used for measurement and analysis. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in refining and validating regression models for stature estimation across different populations, with an emphasis on enhancing the accuracy of predictions [3].

The importance of population-specific data in anthropometric studies cannot be overstated. Stature estimation models developed for one population may not be applicable to another due to genetic, environmental, and nutritional differences that influence growth patterns. Recent research has emphasized the need for creating region-specific equations to improve the reliability of forensic reconstructions [4]. Studies conducted in diverse populations, including those in South Asia, have highlighted variations in limb proportions, which

necessitate the development of localized regression models for accurate stature estimation [5].

Moreover, advancements in statistical techniques and the use of software like SPSS for data analysis have enhanced the precision of these regression models. Contemporary studies have increasingly utilized these tools to assess the relationship between limb measurements and stature, allowing for the development of more robust predictive models [6].

The study aims to estimate stature using humerus length among the adult population.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Tertiary Care Hospital. The research was carried out from March 2023 to March 2024.

Participants: A total of 140 adult participants were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Adults aged 18 years and above.
2. Individuals with no history of skeletal deformities or surgeries affecting the humerus.
3. Participants who provided informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

1. A history of fractures or conditions affecting bone length.
2. Any congenital or acquired skeletal abnormalities.
3. Conditions such as arthritis that could affect joint measurements.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the eligible population.

Measurement bias was reduced by training the personnel involved in data collection and ensuring standardized procedures for all measurements.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured performa. The length of the humerus was measured using a digital vernier caliper. The stature of each participant was measured using a stadiometer, with the participant standing upright without shoes.

Procedure: Participants were asked to sit comfortably while the length of the humerus was measured from the proximal point of the shoulder (acromion process) to the distal point at the elbow (lateral epicondyle). Each measurement was taken three times, and the average value was recorded to ensure accuracy. The stature was then recorded as the standing height of the participants.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and analyzed using SPSS software version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, including means and standard deviations for continuous variables. Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the relationship between humerus length and stature. A regression analysis was conducted to develop a predictive equation for estimating stature based on humerus length. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 140 adult participants were included in the study, comprising 75 males (53.6%) and 65 females (46.4%). The mean age of the participants was 35.7 years (SD = 10.2 years), with an age range of 18 to 65 years. The mean stature was 167.4 cm (SD = 8.5 cm), while the mean humerus length was 30.2 cm (SD = 2.1 cm).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Study Population

Variable	Mean ± SD	Minimum	Maximum
Age (years)	35.7 ± 10.2	18	65
Stature (cm)	167.4 ± 8.5	150.2	185.6
Humerus Length (cm)	30.2 ± 2.1	25.5	34.8

A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to assess the relationship between humerus length and stature. The analysis revealed a strong positive correlation between humerus length and stature ($r = 0.82$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that as the length of the humerus increases, so does the stature.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Between Humerus Length and Stature

Variable	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Humerus Length	0.82	<0.001

A linear regression analysis was performed to develop a predictive model for estimating stature based on humerus length. The regression equation obtained was:
 Stature (cm) = $45.1 + 4.05 \times$ Humerus Length (cm)

The regression model was statistically significant ($F(1, 138) = 210.3, p < 0.001$), with an R-squared value of 0.67, indicating that approximately 67% of the variation in stature could be explained by the humerus length.

Table 3: Linear Regression Analysis

Predictor	Coefficient (B)	Standard Error	t-value	p-value
Constant	45.1	8.3	5.43	<0.001
Humerus Length (cm)	4.05	0.28	14.49	<0.001

To assess the influence of gender on the relationship between humerus length and stature, a stratified analysis was conducted. The results indicated that the correlation between humerus length and stature was slightly stronger in males ($r = 0.84, p < 0.001$) compared to females ($r = 0.79, p$

< 0.001). The regression equations for males and females were as follows:

- Males: Stature (cm) = $42.3 + 4.12 \times \text{Humerus Length (cm)}$
- Females: Stature (cm) = $48.7 + 3.98 \times \text{Humerus Length (cm)}$

Table 4: Gender-Based Linear Regression Analysis

Gender	Predictor	Coefficient (B)	Standard Error	t-value	p-value
Males	Constant	42.3	7.9	5.36	<0.001
	Humerus Length (cm)	4.12	0.27	15.26	<0.001
Females	Constant	48.7	8.1	6.01	<0.001
	Humerus Length (cm)	3.98	0.29	13.72	<0.001

A residual analysis was performed to check the assumptions of the linear regression model. The residuals were approximately normally distributed, and there was no evidence of heteroscedasticity, indicating that the model was appropriate for the data.

Discussion

The study aimed to estimate stature using humerus length among an adult population, involving 140 participants. The results indicated a strong positive correlation between humerus length and stature, with a correlation coefficient of 0.82, suggesting that as humerus length increases, stature also increases. This significant correlation underscores the reliability of using humerus length as a predictor of stature.

A linear regression model was developed to estimate stature based on humerus length, resulting in the equation: Stature (cm) = $45.1 + 4.05 \times \text{Humerus Length (cm)}$. The model was statistically significant, explaining 67% of the variation in stature. This finding highlights the model's effectiveness in predicting stature from humerus length with considerable accuracy.

Gender-based analysis revealed slight differences in the relationship between humerus length and stature, with males showing a slightly stronger correlation than females. Separate regression equations were developed for each gender, providing more precise estimates of stature. These findings suggest that while humerus length is a strong overall predictor of stature, gender-specific equations can enhance prediction accuracy.

Overall, the study confirms that humerus length is a valuable anthropometric parameter for estimating stature, with potential applications in forensic science, anthropology, and clinical practice. The developed regression models offer a practical tool for stature estimation, with the potential for further refinement through additional research considering other demographic variables.

A cross-sectional study conducted among medical students in South India aimed to estimate stature using humerus length. The study found significant positive correlations between humerus length and height, particularly in males. The study provided regression equations for estimating height, which were $103.1 + 1.903 \times \text{Arm length}$ for males and $108.34 + 1.608 \times \text{Arm length}$ for females. The study emphasized the utility of these measurements in reconstructive surgeries and forensic investigations [7].

A pilot study in a contemporary Australian sub-population utilized post-mortem computed tomography (PMCT) to estimate stature and biological sex using the humerus. The study found that the vertical diameter of the humeral head was the best indicator for biological sex, while the maximum humeral length was the best predictor for stature. The study proposed preliminary biological sex and stature estimation equations specific to the Australian population [8].

In a study conducted among Nigerians, stature estimation was performed using radiographs of the humerus. The study provided regression equations for stature estimation, which were found to have a high level of reliability with standard errors of 0.41 cm for males and 0.59 cm for females. The study

demonstrated that the humerus is a reliable predictor of stature in the Nigerian population [9].

A study conducted in South India estimated the maximum length of the humerus using measurements of its proximal segments. The study provided simple regression formulae that can be used in forensic investigations to estimate the stature of individuals from bone fragments. The oblique length between the most proximal and distal points over the anatomical neck was identified as the best predictor of humeral length [10].

A study aimed to develop stature estimation formulae for a contemporary Mexican population using the humerus, femur, and tibia. The study found highly significant linear regression models with correlation coefficients of $r = 0.820$ for the female femur and $r = 0.855$ for the male tibia, providing reliable results for stature estimation in the Mexican population [11].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated a significant positive correlation between humerus length and stature among the adult population. The developed regression model provides a reliable method for estimating stature from humerus length, with gender-specific equations offering additional precision. The results suggest that humerus length can be a useful parameter for forensic and anthropometric studies.

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